

EFFECT OF THERMAL TREATMENT ON THE INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF FLAX FIBERS.

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Keywords: Interface toughness, Sustainable composites, Liquid Composite Molding

ABSTRACT

With the use of Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) for composite manufacturing in the transportation industry, the complexity of part shapes and quality requirements have increased tremendously. There is thus a strong need to accurately control and understand liquid flow through porous preforms in order to minimise void formation in composite parts. Capillary issues and wetting affinity between fibers and resin have to be considered to understand and simulate properly the resin flow during processing. Flax fibers are usually considered adequate bio-reinforcements for composites, thanks to their good mechanical properties and low density. Nevertheless their hydrophilic character makes them sensitive to moisture sorption and incompatible with hydrophobic resins. In this work, a thermal treatment aiming to modify the surface chemistry of flax fibers has been applied in order to make the fiber surface more hydrophobic and decrease the sensitivity to water sorption. Measurements on elementary fibers have been performed to quantify the effect of the thermal treatment on surface energy. On the other hand, the thermal treatment could also result in a decrease of the mechanical properties of flax fibers. The decrease of mechanical properties of yarns does not necessarily imply a decrease in the composite mechanical properties if the interfacial properties are enhanced. In order to evaluate effect of treatment on porosity formation and the Inter-Laminar Shear Strength (ILSS) of composites, panels reinforced by both untreated and treated flax fibers were manufactured by Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM), with strictly controlled and identical process parameters. Quantification of voids and results of mechanical tests will be presented, highlighting the effect of thermal treatment on the mechanical behavior of flax yarns and flax reinforced composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) for composite manufacturing in the transportation industry has increased because it is an efficient and low cost process. Nevertheless void formation in composite parts calls for an improved understanding of capillary issues, in order to simulate properly the resin flow during processing. In parallel, the care for more sustainable materials has pushed the composite industry to look increasingly at bio-based reinforcements and resins. Natural fibers are a good alternative to synthetic ones for their mechanical properties and lower density [1-2], but they present the inconvenience of sensitivity to moisture sorption and worse affinity with hydrophobic polymer resins, because of their hydrophilic character [3]. Caring about the sustainability of reinforcements implies to avoid some chemical treatments that could improve affinity with resins generating unhealthy products or waste [4]. Therefore, the chemical surface state and also the water content of the sustainable reinforcements are aspects that are hard to control.

In this work, a thermal treatment aiming to modify the surface chemistry of flax fibers has been applied in order to break down and activate the hemicelluloses to generate free radicals. These free radicals can create crosslinks in flax pectins and the crosslinks make flax fibers less sensitive to humidity absorption [5]. This study focuses at first on the wetting properties of the treated fibers and

the comparison with the ones characterised for untreated fibers. Measurements of static advancing contact angles were carried out through the goniometric technique, in order to determine dispersive and polar components of untreated and treated fibers' surface energy and then evaluate their wetting character. The thermal treatment has an effect on wetting, but it could be harmful for single fiber mechanical properties. However, mechanical properties of a composite are not only controlled by intrinsic mechanical properties of fibers and resin, but also by the compatibility of the components, in other words by the wetting during manufacturing and the fiber-matrix adhesion. Then the infusion of a plate with both untreated and treated reinforcements was carried out with strictly controlled and identical process parameters. Void content was characterised by an optical method in first approach in different locations for each type of reinforcement, showing some benefits of the treatment regarding porosity formation. Mechanical tests in order to evaluate the Inter-Laminar Shear Strength (ILSS) were also carried out.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Flax reinforcements

Quasi-unidirectional flax fabric (Fig.1a) was provided by Libeco (FLAXDRY UD 180[®]). The areal weight and the density are respectively 180 g/m² and 1.45 g/cm³. It is well-known that natural flax fibers have a hydrophilic character that make reinforcements difficult to wet with hydrophobic polymer resins. A thermal treatment modifying chemical composition and wettability of the fiber surface [5] was carried out on the fabric (Fig.1b). Both fabrics were used to manufacture a composite plate with an epoxy resin provided by Gurit. Its commercial designation is SP106[®]. This resin was selected for its rapid curing at room temperature. Dispersive and polar components of its surface tension were also characterized and are presented in this work.

Figure 1: Flax fiber reinforcements. a) untreated and b) treated.

2.2 Test liquids

Test liquids used in this study to evaluate surface energy and tension of fibers and resin were chosen for their polar γ_L^p and dispersive components γ_L^d (Tab.1). Water is certainly the most common liquid. N-Hexane is a perfectly wetting liquid thanks to its low surface tension and absence of polar component. Diiodomethane has the particularity to be a totally dispersive liquid but with a relatively high surface tension.

Test liquid	γ_L [mN/m]	γ_L^p [mN/m]	γ_L^d [mN/m]
Water	72.8	21.8	51.0
Diiodomethane	50.8	0.0	50.8
N-Hexane	18.4	0.0	18.4

Table 1: Test liquid properties at 20°C.

2.3 Contact angles and surface energy characterization for elementary fibers

A DCAT11 tensiometer (DataPhysics Instrument GmbH, Fildestardt) was used to perform static wettability experiments. This tensiometer is provided with an electronic microbalance (resolution of 10 μg) to which the tested fiber is clamped. The test liquid vessel can move up and down via a piezo-actuated support. All the tests were carried out under standardized conditions, at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and monitored by a camera (uEye, 1024 x 1024 pixels up to 150 frames/s) as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Schematic of the set-up.

For static tests with elementary fibers, the liquid vessel moves up at a velocity of 0.5 mm/s until the microbalance detects a change of weight (given by the capillary force). From this position, the weight of the liquid meniscus formed at the surface of the fiber can be recorded and images acquired in parallel. Thus this system allows carrying out tensiometric and optic measurements. However, for elementary fibers the resolution of the DCAT is not sufficient to obtain precise measurements of meniscus weight. Therefore in this case it was only used to detect the instant when the fiber surface was wetted by liquid and measures of static advancing contact angles were obtained from image analysis: an edge detection locates the liquid/air interface which is then extrapolated and fitted with a sixth order polynomial curve. By derivation of the polynomial fit at the fluid-solid interface ($x=0$) an apparent static advancing contact angle θ_s can be determined on both sides of the fiber. This procedure has been validated on glass rods before, was applied on yarns in previous studies [5] and is used here on elementary fibers (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Example of polynomial fit of right liquid meniscus for an elementary flax fiber wetted by diiodomethane.

The surface energy is then calculated from angles obtained with two different test liquids (one totally dispersive as diiodomethane) according to the Owens and Wendt relation [6]:

$$\gamma_L (1 + \cos \theta_s) = 2(\gamma_s^d \gamma_L^d)^{0.5} + 2(\gamma_s^p \gamma_L^p)^{0.5} \quad (12)$$

2.4 Surface tension components characterization of the resin

To characterize dispersive γ_R^d and polar γ_R^p components of resin, it is possible to use the Owens and Wendt equation (Eq. 1) replacing in this the definition of static contact angle given by the Young-Laplace equilibrium and measuring an interfacial tension (γ_{RL}) between the resin and a test liquid with a totally dispersive surface tension. Then the equation of Owens and Wendt to calculate components becomes:

$$\gamma_R^d = \frac{(\gamma_L + \gamma_R - \gamma_{RL})^2}{4\gamma_L} \quad (2)$$

N-hexane was selected as totally dispersive liquid because it also shows a lower density than the SP106[®] resin from Gurit. In particular, the procedure consists of three steps. First the force due to Archimedes' principle on Wilhelmy's plate is recorded when the plate is immersed in n-hexane (Fig. 4a). In the second step, surface tension of resin γ_R is determined by the standard measure of meniscus formed between the Wilhelmy's plate and the resin (Fig. 4b). Finally n-hexane is added on top of the resin and the interfacial tension γ_{RL} can thus be measured by weighing the meniscus between the resin and n-hexane (Fig. 4c). Knowing the surface tension of resin and the purely dispersive behavior of n-hexane, polar and dispersive components of the resin can be calculated through Eq. 2.

Figure 4: (a) Archimedes' force measurement for n-hexane. (b) Surface tension measurement for resin. (c) Interfacial tension measurement between resin and n-hexane.

2.5 Infusion of composite plate and porosity characterization

A composite plate was manufactured by Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM). The infusion configuration used for this test is described in Fig. 5. The aim was to manufacture plates using both reinforcements, untreated and treated flax fibers, in a single infusion ($[0^\circ]_{10}$) with the same processing conditions for the two types of reinforcements. A distribution medium was placed under the preform to ensure the resin feeding. Another distribution medium was placed under the vent, which is located at the center of the top of the plate, to ensure the quality of the vacuum on the upper part of the preform. The infusion with the SP106[®] was performed at room temperature. A 1.4 mbars vacuum was pulled, and resin was left entering until it arrived in the outlet silicon pipe.

Figure 5: Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) strategy.

Once the plate was obtained, samples for mechanical tests were cut. Three samples for optical observations have also been prepared at the same location on each half of the plate. Those samples have been numbered from 1 to 3 referring to their distance from the vent (1 being the closest). After polishing, micrographs at a magnification of x20 were reconstructed to obtain a picture of the entire sample (Fig. 6). This allows us to characterize the local void content by optical methods.

Figure 6: Reconstructed image of a polished sample.

2.5 MECHANICAL TESTS: SHORT BEAM SHEAR TESTS

Short beam shear tests have been conducted following ASTM D2344 [7] in order to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength of both composites reinforced by treated and untreated flax fibers. Five samples of each type of composite have been tested. The dimensions of the samples were $5 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$ and the thicknesses were measured as 3 mm for untreated flax reinforcements and 3.2 mm for treated reinforcements. This leads to a small difference in the fiber volume ratio (41.4% for flax fibers and 38.8% for treated flax fibers). To assess a failure in agreement with the standard (shear at the neutral axis) the spacing of the two bottom loading points has to be five times the thickness of the sample. It thus was set to 16 mm (Fig. 7).

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: a) Short Beam Shear bench; b) Sample after failure.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Static advancing contact angles and surface energies

Measurements of contact angles have been performed on four different fibers of each type and for each test liquid (diiodomethane and water). Examples of images acquired by camera are shown in Fig. 8. Angles have been measured with the method described in paragraph 2.3. Angles obtained with this method were used to calculate surface energies according to Eq. 1.

Results are presented in table 2. It is shown that static advancing contact angles for untreated flax fibers tend to be lower with water and higher with diiodomethane. It is the opposite for treated flax fibers implying a more dispersive behaviour for treated flax fibers, which was the aim of the thermal treatment. However, the large dispersion in results, which is typical for natural fibers, does not allow concluding on the relevance of the treatment to effect surface energy.

Figure 8: Some images for static advancing contact angle measurement on elementary fibers by optical method.

Sample	Water θ_s	Diiodomethane θ_s	γ_s^p [mN/m]	γ_s^d [mN/m]
Flax	25.1±3.2	32.5±5.5	29.35±2.12	43.15±2.74
Treated Flax	30.6±3.0	26.9±4.1	25.77±1.84	45.45±1.79

Table 2: Results of static advancing contact angle measurements and surface energy of fibers.

3.2 Surface tension of the resin

The method described in paragraph 2.4 has been applied to the SP106[®] resin, using n-Hexane as totally dispersive liquid. Measured surface tension γ_R and interfacial tension γ_{RL} are shown in Table 4, with dispersive (γ_R^d) and polar (γ_R^p) components of the resin calculated through Eq. 2. It appears that

the resin is mostly dispersive. It is consistent with making the fibers more hydrophobic to ease their wetting during LCM processes.

γ_R	γ_{RL}	γ_R^d	γ_R^p	[mN m ⁻¹]
40.35±0.54	7.39±0.34	35.82±0.48	4.53±0.07	

Table 4: Surface tension and its components for the SP106[®] epoxy resin from Gurit.

3.3 Characterization of porosities

Samples for void characterization have been polished and images have been reconstructed. Fig.10 and 11 show voids in both the composite reinforced by treated and untreated flax fibers. Table 5 summarizes the measured void ratio on the cross-sections of the samples. Samples referred to as 1 are the closest to the vent and the ones referred to as 3 are the farthest.

Figure 10: Porosities in an untreated flax reinforced composite.

Figure 11: Porosities in a treated flax reinforced composite.

It is obvious that the void content in the composite reinforced by treated flax fibers is lower. This tends to prove that the treated fibers are better wetted by the resin. Another interesting result is that the void content is higher if the sample is farther from the vent in the case of the treated flax fibers. This is common in composites manufactured by LCM processes [8]. In untreated flax fibers, the void content is rather constant even if samples farther from the vent are considered. This could indicate a problem in wetting of untreated flax fibers.

Sample		Measured void ratio
Flax 1	[%]	2.7±0.4
Flax 2	[%]	2.6±0.6
Flax 3	[%]	2.7±0.6
Treated 1	[%]	1.2±0.4
Treated 2	[%]	1.6±0.4
Treated 3	[%]	2.0±0.4

Table 5: Voids measurements by optical method.

3.4 Mechanical tests: Short Beam Shear tests

The force against displacement curve for short beam shear tests is presented in Fig. 12. The trend for untreated flax is not linear. This is due to a gradual damaging of the composite since the curve is linear at the beginning of loading [9]. The trend for composites reinforced by treated flax fibers is linear until failure which is typical for non-biobased composite when using this mechanical test. Besides, the untreated flax composite shows a non-standard failure that is to say a failure at the bottom of the coupon and not at the neutral axis. This would indicate a more complex loading case and thus several interpretations can be given.

Figure 12: Short beam shear response of composites reinforced by treated and untreated flax.

Coupon number	Force end of linear behaviour [N]	Ultimate force [N]	Shear first damage [MPa]	Shear Ultimate force [MPa]
Flax 1	335	599	16.5	29.9
Flax 2	328	571	16.5	28.5
Flax 3	333	581	16.2	29.0
Flax 4	331	570	16.6	28.5
Flax 5	323	564	15.7	28.2
Treated 1	424	424	19.6	19.6
Treated 2	456	456	21.2	21.2
Treated 3	394	394	18.7	18.7
Treated 4	377	377	16.8	16.8
Treated 5	430	430	19.7	19.7

Table 6: Results on shear stress at first and ultimate damage by short beam shear tests.

The maximum shear stress at the neutral axis has been calculated for composite reinforced by treated and untreated flax both at first damage (loss of linear trend - Table 6) and at failure. The shear stress was estimated to be 19.2 ± 1.6 MPa for composites reinforced by treated fibers. For untreated flax fibers, it is more complicated to draw conclusions. If we consider the loss of linear trend as first damage, the shear at the neutral axis was estimated to be 16.3 ± 0.4 MPa. But if we consider the stress at failure for the same composites, the shear strength was calculated as 28.8 ± 0.7 MPa. If we consider the first value, the increase in strength after treatment is significant even if the fibre volume fraction is lower for treated flax fibers. This increase in strength could be considered as an additional result to prove that the fibers are well wetted by the resin if we assume that it is a consequence from the smaller

content of microvoids. But, if we consider the second value, a decrease in strength is significant. This could be due to a modification of the fibers itself. It appears that they are more brittle after treatment. This is indeed a drawback of this treatment and its effects have to be characterized by other mechanical tests. Also, the treatment level should be adjusted.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A comparison between wetting properties of treated flax fibers and untreated fibers has been conducted with different methods. Measurements of static advancing contact angles were carried out by the goniometric technique, proving an augmentation of the dispersive component of the flax fiber surface energy with the treatment, that is to say showing a less hydrophilic behaviour. These results have to be confirmed by dynamic wetting measurements but this should be beneficial for the wetting with a resin that has been proved to be mainly dispersive. Then the infusion of a plate with both untreated and treated reinforcements was carried out with strictly controlled and identical process parameters. Void content was characterised by an optical method in first approach in different locations for each type of reinforcement, showing a decrease of void content in a composite reinforced with treated fibers. This result has to be confirmed in further studies with a 3D tomographic analysis of void content. The thermal treatment has a positive effect on wetting, but it could be harmful for single fiber mechanical properties. Mechanical properties will be characterised in further studies because the choice has been made in the present study to focus on the compatibility of components, in other words on the wetting during manufacturing with a dispersive resin. Mechanical tests in order to evaluate the Inter-Laminar Shear Strength (ILSS) were also carried out, indicating a modification of fibers' behavior after treatment. It thus has been proved that the thermal treatment has a significant effect on the surface properties of flax fibers. Further studies will focus on the properties of treated fibers themselves. Mechanical properties, swelling under water sorption and accurate void content characterisation with 3D tomography will be carried out.

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